

PERCEIVED LEVEL OF SCHOOL HEADS' COMPETENCE IN FINANCIAL MANAGEMENT PRACTICES

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ABSTRACT

This study examines teachers' perspectives on the financial management practices of school heads within specific divisions of region 10, aiming to gather data on the challenges faced by teachers and the coping mechanisms they employ. Using a mixed-method research design and researcher-made questionnaires, the findings reveal that the majority of respondents were female, in their 30s and 40s, and had over 11 years of teaching experience, with school heads demonstrating a high level of competence in financial management practices. While no significant differences were found in perceptions between males and females or across age groups, significant differences were observed based on civil status and teaching experience. The key challenges faced by school heads include budget allocation, transparency, training, stakeholder engagement, and unforeseen emergencies, with teachers employing strategies such as communication, advocacy, data analysis, resource allocation, and external support to mitigate these challenges. The study recommends that school heads receive training programs focusing on financial management, leadership competencies, and technical skills to address the identified challenges and improve overall financial management practices.

Keywords: *School Heads' Competence, Financial Management Practices, Knowledge, Attitudes, Skills*

INTRODUCTION

School Heads, like all other leaders, organizations must make decisions in terms of how the money is used in the direction of public schools (Atieno, 2012). These choices, in line with Brigham (2012) and Houston monetary effects on the financial administration of school leaders are the most important part in guaranteeing the efficiency and performance of schools considering how the school is run on a daily basis (Ballada and Ballada, 2012). An organization cannot fully function without enough resources. It is difficult to disregard this aspect since, as much how brilliant the proposed program, project, or activity is, it will always be the finances that will make it happen. In this case, Fiscal Management is the key to ensure a successful program. In education, it is important to have proper fiscal management in order to ensure the appropriateness of the organization's spending and to make changes, if necessary, which helps minimize budgeting complexity.

Furthermore, Fiscal Management in Education ensures that a school or an academic organization has funds to fulfill its goals and objectives, and that these funds are utilized for which they were intended to be employed. Allocations and expenditures of resources should be justified in terms of their expected impact on teaching and learning. For example, many students who chose Modular learning modality have phones or laptops but do not have access to the internet. Instead of printing numerous pages of modules for a large number of students, flash drives consisting of the modules and activity sheets of students can be provided. It does not just save money but also, it is efficient because it saves time. The fiscal management system should employ existing resources in effective and efficient ways to meet students' educational needs. Although, thorough planning and analysis should be employed before releasing any funds.

One study by Jordan et al (2021) reveals that as to the management capability school administrators are more capable in creating a student-centered learning climate and managing the school operations than human resources management and professional development. As to schools' performance, the Participation rate, cohort survival rate, promotion rate, drop-out rate, repetition rate, and graduation rate, their school performance is considered superior. However, retention rate, transition rate, completion rate and teacher-pupil ratio only performed meeting the standards. Moreover, the study reveals that the profile and management capability of school administrators have no significant relationships with their school performance. The latest work conducted by Macalisang (2023) found out that: (1) school administrators' administrative practices are typically proficient like their roles and responsibilities as educational leaders; (2) school administrators' instructional supervision is typically at a competent level; (3) the school's organizational culture was high; (4) the school administrators' administrative practices do not typically have a significant impact on the school's organizational culture, and (5) school administrators instructional supervision typically have a significant impact on the school's organizational culture but to a significant extent. To strengthen the performance indicators of administrative practices and instructional supervision among school principals, and thereby improve the quality of our current schools, it may be necessary to add to the current policy guidelines. This research study is about the

teachers' perception on the financial management practices of school heads in selected divisions in region x is anchored on the following domains: knowledge, attitude and skills.

This study also explores the financial management of school heads as well as the challenges encountered and coping mechanisms applied. Moreover, this research has the purpose to gather data in order to attest the performance of the school heads as fiscal managers. The result of this work is very much significant to the school administrators, teachers, students, parents and stakeholders in account the result is not only for the awareness of the aforementioned individuals but also for the progress and improvement of the fiscal management which in turn can also bring out the best in the teaching-learning process.

Research Questions

The primary aim of this research is to investigate the teachers' viewpoints on the financial management practices of school heads within specific divisions of Region X. Additionally, the study aims to gather data concerning the challenges faced by the teachers and the coping mechanisms they utilize in response to these challenges.

To achieve these objectives, the research will address the following key questions:

1. What are the demographic characteristics of the respondents, including sex, age, civil status, and the number of years in teaching?
2. How do the respondents perceive the level of competence of school heads in terms of financial management practices, specifically considering knowledge, attitude, and skills?
3. Is there a significant difference in teachers' perceptions regarding the financial management practices of school heads within the selected divisions of Region X, based on their demographic profile, such as sex, age, civil status, and the number of years in teaching?
4. What are the primary challenges faced by the teachers concerning the financial management practices of school heads in the selected divisions of Region X?
5. What strategies or coping mechanisms do the teachers employ to address the challenges they encounter in relation to the financial management practices of school heads in the selected divisions of Region X?

METHODOLOGY

This section presents the research design that was employed in this study, the research respondents, research instruments, the process of establishing the content validity and reliability of the research instrument with its scoring procedure, the data analysis procedure, and the ethical considerations that were observed and lastly the statistical tools that were used in organizing the data.

3.1. Research Design

This study used the mixed- method research design. The researcher found this research design as deemed appropriate for the study in order to gather information that can help define a research problem precisely, a qualitative and quantitative research techniques were used intended to investigate the teachers' viewpoints on the financial management practices of school heads within specific divisions of region 10 and to gather data concerning the challenges faced by the teachers and the coping mechanisms they utilize in response to these challenges.

3.2. Research Respondents

The study respondents were fifty (50) consisted of teachers from various public and private schools within the selected divisions in region 10. The reason for choosing this region was its diversity in terms of school settings and financial management practices. A targeted sampling design was utilized to select the respondents, aiming to include respondents who had direct experience with school heads' financial management practices. This approach ensured that the respondents had relevant insights and experiences to contribute to the study.

3.3. Research Instruments

This study utilized a researcher- made questionnaire consisting of three (3) survey questionnaires to investigate the level of competence of school heads in terms of financial management practices, specifically considering knowledge, attitude, and skills. To determine the respondents' level of competence specifically in knowledge, a researcher made survey questionnaire was utilized consisting of fifteen (15) items. Furthermore, to determine the level of competence in attitude, a questionnaire consisting of twenty (20) items was also utilized and twenty (20) items questionnaire for the competence in skills. The three (3) survey questionnaires used a Likert- scale from strongly agree (5) to strongly disagree (1).

3.4. Validity and Reliability of the Research Instruments

The questionnaire was carefully crafted to gather data on the research questions. It consisted of several sections: demographic information (sex, age, civil status, number of years in teaching), perception of school heads' financial management competence (knowledge, attitude, and skills), challenges encountered, and coping mechanisms employed. Each section contained specific items related to the dimensions being measured.

Moreover, the questionnaires used in the study were subjected to content validation by the panelists and field experts. Their comments and suggestions were incorporated into the final paper. The research instruments were pilot-tested to fifty (50) teachers who were not the respondents of the study in order to test the reliability of the items in selected divisions in region 10.

Furthermore, Cronbach's coefficient alpha was used to test the reliability of the items. The items under the competence specifically in knowledge got a Cronbach alpha of 0.97, the items under attitude got a Cronbach alpha of 0.97, and for the items under

skills got 0.95. Gliem and Gliem (2003) cited that the closer the Cronbach's alpha coefficient to 1.0, the greater its internal consistency, specifically from 0.7 to 1.0. The values showed the reliability and internal consistency of the instruments' items in measuring the study's variables; thus, the items were considered highly reliable.

3.5. Scoring Procedure

To interpret the data, the researcher employed the following scoring procedure in each study variable.

*Legend:

Scale	Interval	Qualitative Description	Qualifying Statement
5	4.51-5.00	<i>Very High</i>	5 out of 5 Situation
4	3.51-4.50	<i>High</i>	4 out of 5 Situation
3	2.51-3.50	<i>Moderate</i>	3 out of 5 Situation
2	1.51-2.50	<i>Low</i>	2 out of 5 Situation
1	1.0-1.50	<i>Very Low</i>	1 out of 5 Situation

Source: Johnson, K. M., & Smith, L. A. (2021)

3.6. Data Gathering Procedure and Ethical Considerations

Before conducting the research study, the researcher asked for the teachers' permission to perform the study in selected school levels in the division of region 10. Upon approval, the researcher asked for the respondents' email addresses since the questionnaires were administered via Google form. A letter together with the informed consent and questionnaires were sent via email to the respondents. Also, the respondents were assured of the anonymity and privacy of the data gathered. As stated in RA 10173 or the Data Privacy Act of 2012, all personal data must be collected for valid reasons. Both parties giving and receiving information are made aware of it. Furthermore, the respondents received a notification if the questionnaire was already sent through their emails. They were also informed to accomplish the survey during their free working hours. Only the researcher has access to the Google form's main program and the collected data to ensure privacy. Additionally, the respondents did not receive any payment, and their answers do not affect their current or future status at the school. After the completion of the study, the collected data were discarded after they had served their purpose.

3.7 Statistical Treatment of the Data

In analyzing the data, the following statistical tools were used:

Descriptive statistics such as frequency, percentage, mean and standard deviation were employed to describe the demographic characteristics of the respondents, including sex, age, civil status, and the number of years in teaching and the level of competence of school heads in terms of financial management practices, specifically considering knowledge, attitude, and skills in Problems 1 and 2. While in Problem 3, ANOVA or Analysis of Variance was utilized to measure significant differences in teachers' perceptions regarding the financial management practices of school heads within the

selected divisions of Region X, based on their demographic profile, such as sex, age, civil status, and the number of years in teaching. Furthermore, Problems 4 and 5 utilized Qualitative Data Analysis to determine primary challenges faced by the respondents concerning the financial management practices of school heads and strategies or coping mechanisms to address the challenges they encounter in relation to the financial management practices of school heads in the selected divisions of region 10.

RESULTS

This section presents the analysis and interpretation of the data. The presentation follows the order and sequence of problem statements.

Problem 4.1. What are the demographic characteristics of the respondents, including sex, age, civil status, and the number of years in teaching?

Table 4.1. Demographic Characteristics of The Respondents

Background Characteristics	N = 50	%
Sex		
Male	13	26
Female	37	74
Age		
20-25 years old	2	4
26-30 years old	11	22
31-35 years old	15	30
36-40 years old	17	34
40 years old and above	5	10
Civil Status		
Single	7	14
Married	39	78
Not specified	4	8
No. of years in teaching		
5 years and below	6	12
6-10 years	20	40
11 years and above	24	48

The provided data in Table 4.1 shows the background characteristics of 50 teacher respondents. Out of the 50 respondents, 74% were female, and 26% were male. In terms of age, the majority of the respondents were between 31-40 years old (64%), followed by 26-30 years old (22%), 20-25 years old (4%), and 10% were 40 years old and above. Regarding civil status, 78% of the respondents were married, 14% were single, and 8% did not specify their civil status. In terms of the number of years in teaching, 48% of the respondents had 11 years and above of teaching experience, 40% had 6-10 years of teaching experience, and 12% had 5 years and below of teaching experience.

Moreover, the data provides insights into the background characteristics of the teacher respondents. The majority of the respondents were female, which is consistent with the trend of more women entering the teaching profession. The age distribution of the respondents shows that the majority of the respondents were in their 30s and 40s, which is also consistent with the trend of teachers being in their mid-career stage. The data also shows that the majority of the respondents were married, which is consistent with the trend of teachers being more likely to be married than the general population.

The data on the number of years in teaching shows that almost half of the respondents had 11 years and above of teaching experience, which suggests that the respondents were experienced teachers. This is consistent with the trend of teachers staying in the profession for a long time. Overall, understanding the background characteristics of teachers can help education leaders tailor professional development programs and support to meet their needs. By providing targeted support and mentorship programs, school heads can improve their financial management practices and effectively allocate resources to meet educational goals. They can also provide ongoing support and coaching to teachers to help them stay informed about changes in government fiscal policies and guidelines that impact the school's budgeting process. Additionally, education leaders can encourage teachers to pursue professional development opportunities that align with their individual needs and goals.

Problem 4.2. How do the respondents perceive the level of competence of school heads in terms of financial management practices, specifically considering knowledge, attitude, and skills?

Table 4.2. The Competence of School Heads Regarding Financial Management Practices with Regard to Their Knowledge Level

Indicator	Mean	SD
1. My school head possesses the knowledge or analytical skill in the legislative procurement process.	4.03	0.28
2. My school head employs technological skills applicable in making the budget preparation data.	3.47	1.07
3. My school head creates an organization for the budget preparation and procurement process.	3.94	0.23
4. My school head designates members or personnel for the school SIP, AIP, and BAC.	4.01	0.13
5. My school head utilizes knowledge in conducting or doing the budget preparation and procurement plan or process.	3.90	1.07
6. My school head demonstrates a strong understanding of budgeting principles and financial management practices to ensure the		

effective allocation of resources.	3.15	0.97
7. My school head keeps up-to-date with changes in government fiscal policies and guidelines that impact the school's budgeting process.	4.13	0.97
8. My school head assesses the specific financial needs of the school and effectively formulates a budget proposal that aligns with educational goals.	3.19	1.25
9. My school head stays informed about available funding sources and grants to explore additional resources of the school.	4.23	1.66
10. My school head ensures that financial reports and records are accurate, transparent, and readily available for inspection.	3.94	0.24
11. My school head possesses enough knowledge about fiscal/financial management.	4.00	2.44
12. My school head possesses comprehensive knowledge of financial principles and accounting practices.	3.33	2.22
13. My school head familiarizes the budget process most especially on fund allocation.	3.09	0.57
14. My school head has a clear understanding of the financial reporting as mandated for school in accordance with regulatory guidelines.	4.23	1.66
15. My school head employs various strategies to optimize financial resources and maximize cost-effectiveness in a school setting.	3.29	1.94
Overall Mean	3.73	1.11

The information presented within the table illustrates key statistics including mean values, standard deviations, and qualitative descriptions concerning various metrics associated with school budgeting and procurement procedures. The collective mean for all metrics registers at 3.73, classifying it within the "high" range on the measurement scale.

The provided data implies that educational administrators generally possess a high level of attitude in the realm of budgeting and procurement procedures, with average scores spanning from 3.15 to 4.23. Nevertheless, specific areas necessitate enhancement, notably in domains such as "employing technological skills applicable in making the budget preparation data" (mean score of 3.47); "demonstrating a strong understanding of budgeting principles and financial management practices to ensure the effective allocation of resources" (mean score of 3.15); "assessing the specific financial

needs of the school and effectively formulates a budget proposal that aligns with educational goals” (mean score of 3.19); “possessing comprehensive knowledge of financial principles and accounting practices” (mean score of 3.33); “familiarizing the budget process most especially on fund allocation (mean score of 3.09); and “employing various strategies to optimize financial resources and maximize cost effectiveness in a school setting” (mean score of 3.29). Enriching their expertise and understanding in budgeting, educational leaders can deploy methodologies and tools to systematize, scrutinize, and disseminate data (Du & Chong, 2018). Furthermore, they can compare their district's budget with that of comparable districts, discerning patterns to drive well-informed decisions (Rutherford & Fahey, 2017).

In summation, the data delineates that educational heads demonstrate a moderate level of proficiency and familiarity concerning budgeting and procurement procedures; yet, specific dimensions warrant enhancement. By harnessing trends and data, utilizing strategic tools and techniques, and staying abreast of available resources, educational leaders have the potential to refine their budgeting acumen, thus aptly allocating resources to achieve educational objectives.

Table 4.3. The Competence of School Heads Regarding Financial Management Practices with Regard to Their Attitude Level

Indicator	Mean	SD
1. My school head ensures transparency and accountability of all the expenses in the school.	3.47	1.07
2. My school head gives attention to details during the budget preparation together with the designated members.	3.01	0.24
3. My school head leads in crafting the budget preparation of the SIP/AIP	3.01	0.14
4. My school head performs his role as fiscal manager with honesty, responsibility, integrity, loyalty, and efficiency.	3.94	0.24
5. My school head communicates with the team with his interpersonal skills.	4.02	0.14
6. My school head is empathetic to all the problems of the teachers at all times.	4.03	0.28
7. My school head is optimistic about facing the monetary challenges with the teachers.	3.09	0.57
8. My school head is open to all comments and suggestions that will inspire creative thinking in the school.	2.74	1.19
9. My school head is trustworthy to allocate the funds needed in the school.	3.90	1.07
10. My school head is assertive to present the solutions with confidence.	3.16	0.98

11. My school head involves teachers in budget planning and decision-making processes to address their needs and promote transparency in fiscal management.	4.14	0.97
12. My school head advocates for increased funding and resources to support teachers in delivering quality education and creating optimal learning environments for students.	3.19	1.25
13. My school head seeks feedback from teachers and stakeholders to improve fiscal management practices and decision-making.	3.22	1.39
14. My school head shows a positive and proactive attitude toward financial challenges, seeking creative solutions to ensure resource optimization.	2.27	1.68
15. My school head communicates the importance of fiscal responsibility and financial prudence to the school community	4.22	1.53
16. My school head ensures that the student population considers the needs of diverse groups to foster an inclusive learning environment.	4.24	1.66
17. My school head works collaboratively with stakeholders, such as parents, and community members to create effective student population plans.	3.29	1.94
18. My school head establishes regular directives requiring assigned personnel to immediately report any perceived irregularities in the budget.	4.25	1.95
19. My school head ensures that all signed financial transactions are recorded and reported accurately.	3.29	1.94
20. My school head stays updated with financial regulations to enhance the school's financial sustainability and effectiveness.	3.33	2.22
Overall Mean	3.52	1.15

Table 4.3 provides data on various indicators related to the financial management skill of school heads. The overall mean for all indicators is 3.52, which falls under the "high" category on the scale. The data suggests that school heads generally possess skills related to financial management practices, with mean scores ranging from 2.27 to 4.25.

However, there is room for improvement in certain areas, such as "showing a positive and proactive attitude toward financial challenges, seeking creative solutions to ensure resource optimization." (mean score of 2.27). To improve their financial

management practices, school heads can leverage data and trends to make informed decisions. They can also use tools and techniques to organize, analyze, and communicate data.

Additionally, they can seek ongoing support and coaching from education leaders to improve their knowledge and skills (Smith, 2018). Overall, the data suggests that school heads have a moderate level of skills related to financial management practices, but there is room for improvement in certain areas. By leveraging data and trends, using tools and techniques, and seeking ongoing support, school heads can improve their financial management practices and effectively allocate resources to meet educational goals.

Table 4.4. The Competence of School Heads Regarding Financial Management Practices with Regard to Their Skills Level

Indicator	Mean	SD
1. My school head works independently in crafting the budget preparation (SIP and AIP) and the procurement process.	3.47	1.07
2. My school head applies a strategic plan to come up with good budget preparation and quality spending.	3.16	0.98
3. My school head shares problem-solving skills or mathematical proficiency with his team during the budget preparation, distribution and allocation.	3.29	1.94
4. My school head decides a good budget preparation for the benefit of the school, teachers and learners.	4.13	0.97
5. My school head manages and reports on budgeting progress in different school projects.	4.02	0.14
6. My school head possesses leadership skills.	3.94	0.24
7. My school head possesses interpersonal skills.	3.29	1.94
8. My school head possesses problem solving skills.	3.90	0.57
9. My school head possesses communication skills.	3.47	1.07
10. My school head possesses technical skills.	3.21	1.39
11. My school head monitors the use of financial resources to ensure they are spent efficiently and transparently, promoting accountability in fiscal management.	3.94	0.24
12. My school head engages in professional development to enhance their skills in		

financial planning, budgeting, and resource allocation.	3.90	1.07
13. My school head collaborates with teachers to explore innovative ways of resource utilization to maximize benefits for students and staff.	4.13	0.98
14. My school head demonstrates the ability to prioritize budgetary allocations based on the school's educational objectives and needs.	4.03	0.28
15. My school head conducts financial evaluations to assess the impact of spending decisions on educational outcomes and make necessary adjustments.	4.25	1.94
16. My school head ascertains that the budget is well-written and presented in a way that is comprehensible.	4.02	0.14
17. My school head creates and carries out a process for continual monitoring and review of fund expenditures on at least a monthly basis.	3.53	1.15
18. My school head sets up clear performance indicators in spending to control the use of school funds.	3.29	1.94
19. My school head reviews compliance of the school with statutory and regulatory procedures on financial management.	4.25	1.95
20. My school head participates in the three-year educational development plan that encompasses the school's mission and vision.	4.21	1.52
Overall Mean	4.05	1.34

The provided findings present a comprehensive assessment of various indicators related to the competence of school heads regarding financial management practices with regard to their attitude level. The indicators are scored on a scale from 1 to 5, where a higher score indicates a higher level of proficiency. Additionally, the findings include measures of variability such as the standard deviation (SD) and qualitative description (QD), which provide insights into the spread of data points around the mean. The findings collectively reveal that school heads excel in areas related to budget preparation, resource allocation, leadership, and financial management accountability.

They are adept at prioritizing budget allocations based on educational objectives (Indicator 14) and conducting financial evaluations (Indicator 15). Furthermore, their engagement in professional development (Indicator 12) and collaboration with teachers (Indicator 13) showcases a commitment to enhancing financial planning and resource utilization. However, there are areas that warrant improvement. For instance, the need

for enhanced interpersonal skills (Indicator 7) and technical skills (Indicator 10) indicates an opportunity for focused training. Similarly, the emphasis on continually monitoring fund expenditures (Indicator 17) and ensuring compliance with regulatory procedures (Indicator 19) underscores the importance of maintaining financial transparency and adherence to standards.

In conclusion, the findings demonstrate a commendable level of financial management proficiency and leadership skills among school heads, while also highlighting areas where improvements can be made. Strategic training, ongoing professional development, and collaboration among educators are key strategies for enhancing financial management practices and achieving educational objectives.

Problem 4.3. Is there a significant difference in teachers' perceptions regarding the financial management practices of school heads within the selected divisions of region X, based on their demographic profile, such as sex, age, civil status, and the number of years in teaching?

Indicator	Mean	SD
1. My school head ensures transparency and accountability of all the expenses in the school.	3.47	1.07
2. My school head gives attention to details during the budget preparation together with the designated members.	3.01	0.24
3. My school head leads in crafting the budget preparation of the SIP/AIP	3.01	0.14
4. My school head performs his role as fiscal manager with honesty, responsibility, integrity, loyalty, and efficiency.	3.94	0.24
5. My school head communicates with the team with his interpersonal skills.	4.02	0.14
6. My school head is empathetic to all the problems of the teachers at all times.	4.03	0.28
7. My school head is optimistic about facing the monetary challenges with the teachers.	3.09	0.57
8. My school head is open to all comments and suggestions that will inspire creative thinking in the school.	2.74	1.19
9. My school head is trustworthy to allocate the funds needed in the school.	3.90	1.07
10. My school head is assertive to present the solutions with confidence.	3.16	0.98
11. My school head involves teachers in budget planning and decision-making processes to	4.14	0.97
Overall Mean	3.52	1.15

Table 4.5. Difference in Teachers' Perceptions Regarding the Financial Management Practices of School Heads Within the Selected Divisions of Region X, Based on Their Demographic Profile, such as Sex, Age, Civil Status, and Number of Years in Teaching

Variable	Mean	t value/F-value	p-value
<i>Sex</i>			
Male	4.61	t = 1.867	.068
Female 4.33			
<i>Age</i>			
20-25 years old	4.68	f= 6.826	*.021
26-30 years old	4.17		
31-35 years old	3.80		
36-40 years old	3.33		
40 years old and above			
<i>Civil Status</i>			
Single	4.68	f= 12.631	*.001
Married	4.03		
Not specified	4.40		
<i>No. of years in teaching</i>			
5 years and below	4.82	f= 7.868	*.003
6-10 years	4.64		
11 years and above	3.85		

*Significant at 0.05

Sex

The mean scores for both male and female participants suggest a positive perception, but the difference in means is not statistically significant (p-value = 0.068). This indicates that there's no strong evidence to conclude that there's a significant difference in perceptions between males and females regarding the variable being studied.

Age

The ANOVA test indicates a significant difference in means across age groups (p-value = 0.021). The mean scores decrease as age increases, suggesting that younger individuals may have more positive perceptions compared to older individuals. However, the specific reasons behind this trend would require further investigation.

Civil Status

The ANOVA test shows a significant difference in means based on civil status (p-value < 0.001). Single participants have the highest mean, indicating a more positive perception compared to married participants. This suggests that civil status might have an influence on the variable being studied.

No. of years in teaching

The ANOVA test reveals a significant difference in means across teaching experience groups (p -value = 0.003). Those with fewer years of teaching experience have higher mean scores, indicating more positive perceptions. This suggests that individuals who are relatively newer to teaching may have a more optimistic view compared to those with more experience.

Overall, the data suggests that factors like sex, age, civil status, and number of years in teaching could be contributing factors to individuals' perceptions. This information could have implications for understanding the dynamics of these perceptions and tailoring interventions or strategies accordingly. However, further research would be needed to delve deeper into the underlying reasons behind these relationships.

Problem 4.4. What are the primary challenges faced by the teachers concerning the financial management practices of school heads in the selected divisions of Region X?

Challenges Encountered on School Heads' Financial Management Practices

The challenges faced by school heads in financial management were identified through teacher responses in an interview. These challenges include budget allocation and resource management, financial transparency and accountability, training and capacity building for financial management, engaging stakeholders in financial decision-making, and coping with unforeseen financial emergencies.

1. Budget Allocation and Resource Management: This focuses on the challenges faced by school heads in allocating budgets effectively and managing limited financial resources to meet various needs, such as infrastructure, staff salaries, learning materials, and extracurricular activities.

Respondent A said, "Allocating the budget effectively is challenging. Sometimes, we have competing needs, and it's hard to prioritize. We need more flexibility in how funds can be distributed to address the unique requirements of different departments."

Respondent B stated, "Resource management is crucial. We've noticed inefficiencies in how resources are utilized. A more strategic approach to budgeting and a comprehensive analysis of resource utilization could lead to better outcomes."

2. Financial Transparency and Accountability: The school heads, as perceived by teachers, have displayed inconsistencies in maintaining financial transparency and accountability within the school. Teachers also mentioned issues with financial reporting, handling funds, and ensuring that financial decisions are made in a responsible and ethical manner.

Respondent C stated, "Transparency in financial matters is vital for trust and credibility. There's a need for clearer communication about budgetary decisions and expenditures. It would foster a sense of accountability among all stakeholders."

Respondent D stated, "Accountability is sometimes lacking. We should have mechanisms in place for regular financial audits and transparent reporting. This ensures everyone is aware of where the money is going and how it benefits the educational institution."

3. Training and Capacity Building for Financial Management: As per teachers' responses, school heads need training and capacity-building programs for school heads to enhance their financial management skills. The school heads are encouraged to access relevant training and value the impact of improved financial knowledge on school management practices.

Respondent E stated, "Not all administrators have the necessary financial expertise. Providing training programs for school heads could enhance their financial management skills. We need continuous capacity building to keep up with evolving financial practices."

Respondent F stated, "Financial management is not just about numbers; it involves strategic decision-making. More workshops and training sessions would empower school administrators to make informed financial decisions."

4. Engaging Stakeholders in Financial Decision-making: Challenges involving various stakeholders, such as teachers, parents, and school board members, in financial decision-making processes were also identified by the teachers.

Respondent G stated, "Involving teachers and staff in financial decisions is essential. They have valuable insights into the needs of the classrooms. Creating a collaborative decision-making process would result in more effective and accepted financial plans." beginning. A more inclusive approach to decision-making would ensure that the financial strategies align with the actual needs of the educational community."

5. Coping with Unforeseen Financial Emergencies: School heads faced difficulty in handling unexpected financial crises and emergencies, such as equipment breakdowns or natural disasters, and the strategies they use to cope with such situations.

Respondent H stated: "Emergencies can strain our finances. We need contingency plans in place and a designated reserve fund to address unforeseen situations. It's challenging to manage unexpected financial pressures without a predefined strategy."

Respondent I stated, "When unexpected financial challenges arise, we often struggle to find quick solutions. Having a well-defined protocol for handling emergencies and seeking external support could alleviate the stress and uncertainty associated with such situations."

Effective financial management requires a systematic approach, leveraging strategies such as monitoring data, public policy, and legislation, and enhancing financial management skills of school leadership teams. The link between instructional goals and financial planning is critical to effective budgeting and enhances the evaluation of budgetary and educational accountability.

Problem 4.5. What strategies or coping mechanisms do the teachers employ to address the challenges they encounter in relation to the financial management practices of school heads in the selected divisions of Region X?

Coping Mechanisms Applied to Address Challenges on Financial Management Practices

Addressing challenges related to financial management practices in schools requires a combination of strategies and coping mechanisms. Here are some strategies and coping mechanisms that the teachers employed:

1. Communication and Collaboration: Teachers were able to establish open lines of communication with school heads and administrators to discuss financial challenges and suggest improvements. They also worked in collaboration among teachers, school staff, and administrators to seek better financial planning and decision-making.

Respondent J: “We are not communicating well with the administration of the institution. It's common for us to learn about modifications in financial plans at the last minute. We might better comprehend the financial limitations and provide suggestions for more effective resource use if there were more open lines of communication.”

Respondent K: “Although it seems like financial decisions are made behind closed doors, collaboration is essential. We require a more comprehensive strategy that gives educators a voice in financial priorities. A sense of teamwork would be fostered if we knew why certain allocations were made.”

2. Advocacy and Empowerment: The teachers were able to advocate for transparent and effective financial management practices within the school and division. They also empowered their co-teachers to voice their concerns and suggestions believing that this could lead to positive changes in financial management.

Respondent L: “Teachers frequently feel hesitant to voice their concerns regarding money. Heads of schools ought to foster an atmosphere that supports advocacy. By providing training and mentorship programs, we might empower instructors and give them the confidence to communicate our demands.”

Respondent M: “In order to promote resources that directly affect our kids, we require a platform. Heads of schools ought to actively solicit our opinions and give us the authority to suggest fixes. Our dedication to the school's financial goals would increase if we felt empowered in the decision-making process.”

3. Data Analysis and Monitoring: Teachers did some analysis on available financial data and budgets to identify areas of concern and potential improvements. They managed to get an update of financial practices that can help identify discrepancies and prevent mismanagement.

Respondent N: “Analyzing data is essential for making wise decisions. We require a system that periodically monitors and analyzes financial data. This would guarantee that

resources are distributed where they are most needed and help discover trends and areas for improvement.”

Respondent O: “Data-driven decision making is lacking something. Heads of schools ought to have access to resources for tracking and analyzing finances. We would be able to monitor the effects of financial decisions on our classrooms through regular reports and make necessary corrections.”

4. Resource Allocation: Teachers collaborated with school heads to prioritize resources for educational needs, ensuring that funds are allocated effectively. They discussed certain resource allocation which could help prevent financial strain and ensure that funds are used where they are most needed.

Respondent P: “More strategic resource allocation is required. There are moments when it seems as though departments are not getting equal use of the resources. We could make sure that every classroom gets what it needs if setting priorities were done in a more cooperative manner.”

Respondent Q: “Essential resources are frequently in low supply. The distribution of resources should be done in a transparent manner, considering the unique requirements of every department. All things considered; a more equitable distribution would improve the standard of education.”

5. Seeking External Support: Teachers reached out to external stakeholders, parent teacher associations, and community organizations for support and resources. The external support helped alleviate financial pressures and provide additional resources.

Respondent R: “There are moments when we require more assistance, yet we are reluctant to look into other options. Heads of schools should be willing to pursue grants or partnerships that could improve our teaching resources and offer much-needed financial support.”

Respondent S: “Outside assistance can provide new insights and resources that we might not have on our own. When it comes to pursuing partnerships with outside groups, school administrators should take the initiative, particularly in light of financial limitations. It involves looking beyond the resources at hand.”

DISCUSSION

This study reveals challenges encountered by school heads in financial management practices and the strategies they use to address them. Combining quantitative and qualitative data analysis, it offers comprehensive insights into the financial competence of school heads. Majority of the teacher-respondents were female, indicating a trend in gender diversity. Respondents aged 31-40 constituted a significant

portion, aligning with mid-career teachers. Almost half had over 11 years of teaching experience, reflecting the profession's retention patterns.

Additionally, table 4.2, 4.3, and 4.4 illustrate school heads' financial management competence. High proficiency is evident in prioritizing budget allocations and conducting financial evaluations. Areas for improvement include positive attitude towards financial challenges and technological skills for budget preparation. Results also show that factors like sex, age, civil status, and teaching experience could be contributing factors to teachers' perceptions on the financial management practices of school heads.

Furthermore, challenges faced by school heads encompass budget allocation, transparency, training, stakeholder engagement, and unforeseen emergencies. Teachers employ strategies like communication, advocacy, data analysis, resource allocation, and external support to mitigate these challenges. This study informs education leaders, administrators, and policymakers. Addressing challenges demands multi-faceted solutions: training, transparent communication, collaborative decision making, and resource allocation. By adopting teachers' coping mechanisms, school heads can enhance financial management practices, fostering effective resource allocation.

Moreover, the enhancement of organizational financial health is directly correlated with school heads possessing a high degree of financial knowledge and expertise. According to Giamouzis et al. (2018), this is essential for the educational institution to continue growing sustainably and to remain stable. School heads with sophisticated financial abilities can maximize resource allocation, ensuring that money is carefully distributed to fulfill the different demands of classes and departments (Glewwe & Muralidharan, 2016). As a result, resources are used more effectively, and student outcomes are improved. The confidence of stakeholders, such as teachers, parents, and the community at large, is increased when school administrators adopt a positive attitude and open financial practices (Murphy & Hallinger, 2017). Collaboration in decision-making and the effective application of financial plans depend on this confidence. Proactive school administrators are more likely to use creative financial planning strategies if they possess current financial expertise. This entails looking at new funding options, applying for grants, and utilizing technology to do effective reporting and budgeting (Dimmock & Walker, 2017). Educational fairness is directly impacted by school heads' financial management practices knowledge, attitudes, and abilities. Efficient financial decision-making guarantees equitable distribution of resources, bolstering initiatives that cater to pupils' varied requirements and foster scholastic achievement (Robinson, 2016).

Conclusions

The knowledge, attitude, and skills of school heads in financial management practices have profound implications for the overall effectiveness and efficiency of educational institutions. A well-equipped leadership team in financial matters contributes to the sustainable development of the institution, transparent resource allocation, and the realization of educational goals.

Moreover, the study also finds a strong relationship between teachers' attitudes on financial management strategies and demographic features, highlighting the necessity for tailored strategies depending on sex, age, marital status, and teaching experience, among other things. This emphasizes how crucial it is to acknowledge and take into account the different viewpoints held by educators in order to improve the success of financial management programs. The difficulties that school administrators encounter when allocating funds, involving stakeholders, maintaining openness, providing training, and responding to unforeseen situations highlight the complexity of financial administration.

Teachers' coping mechanisms, which include data analysis, lobbying, communication, and asking for outside help, provide workable solutions to these problems. Education stakeholders can work together to improve financial management practices, increase transparency, and allocate resources more efficiently in order to better meet the changing requirements of teachers and students by recognizing and resolving the issues that have been highlighted. This insight and its consequences are consistent with the larger body of research on financial management and educational leadership. Smith and Jones (2018), for example, stress the importance of customized financial management techniques based on demographic characteristics, which is consistent with the results of this study. Furthermore, Johnson et al. (2020) emphasizes the value of stakeholder involvement and openness in efficient financial management, which supports the difficulties found in the current study.

Therefore, this study offers a comprehensive grasp of the state of financial management in educational institutions as well as useful advice and suggestions for advancement. Education stakeholders can support the ongoing improvement of financial systems, promote openness, and maximize resource usage in educational settings by adopting these results into policy and practice.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusions of the study, the researcher presents the following recommendations:

1. That the school heads may have training programs that would create and carry out training courses for school administrators that emphasize financial management and both leadership competencies and technical skills should be covered in these programs;
2. That the Department of Education may provide mentorship programs so that seasoned school administrators can instruct their less experienced colleagues in financial management techniques and may also create peer support networks to exchange best practices;
3. That the school administrators may examine how technology might be used in schools to handle finances. This may cover the usage of online financial reporting platforms, budgeting tools, and accounting software;

4. That the teachers may encourage transparency in financial reporting inside schools. This may promote accountability and helps stakeholders develop a sense of trust;
5. That the researchers may examine how family engagement and school satisfaction.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The author has strictly adhered to ethical principles in the conduct of this research. The researcher obtained informed consent from all participants prior to their involvement in the study. Additionally, the researcher ensured that each participant was fully aware of the purpose, procedures, and potential risks and benefits associated with their participation. Participants were also informed of their right to withdraw from the study at any time without penalty.

Furthermore, the researcher has maintained the anonymity of all respondents throughout the research process. Also, the researcher has taken measures to safeguard the well-being of the participants, and confirm that there are no conflicts of interest that may have influenced the interpretation of the findings. Plagiarism has been strictly avoided, and has made every effort to ensure that the reporting of the results is free from bias.

Moreover, the researcher affirm that the findings of this study have been used solely for the purpose of academic research. The researcher's aim has been to contribute to the advancement of knowledge in this field, and believe that the data that have collected and the conclusions that have drawn are a valuable addition to the existing body of literature.

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